

REPORT

IDS TECHNICAL GAP ANALYSIS

Assessing the readiness of open scholarly infrastructures for an International Data Space role

Authors:

Rich Brown, Head of Technical Delivery, 67 Bricks

Alexandra Howat, Engagement Lead, 67 Bricks

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6396-1373>

Funded via the Mellon Foundation

For more information about this report, contact:

Jennifer Schivas, CEO

jennifer.schivas@67bricks.com

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We've been working in the information industry for over 15 years, and have a roster of clients that includes specialised publishers delivering essential insights to their communities, scholarly publishers dealing with huge amounts of complex data, and business intelligence companies providing critical insights to global decision-makers.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In 2022 The Mellon Foundation awarded funds to OA Books Usage Data Trust (OAeBUDT) to focus on the development of “governance building blocks” to develop governance mechanisms, legal and participatory frameworks and a sustainability model for a minimum viable product (MVP) operational launch of an International Data Space (IDS) in 2025. This OAEBUDT-IDS would aim to deliver the exchange of trusted, scalable, cross-platform Open Access books usage data that is generated by commercial and public platforms and services.

As part of the work towards this, 67 Bricks was engaged to identify operational scholarly publishing service providers that may be able to perform the IDS core functional roles and to assess them against the IDS Reference Architecture Model (RAM) 4.0 and current certification specification documents, noting additional technical or organisational development that would be needed to meet certification and security requirements. 67 Bricks was asked to assess against only this model and was not asked to take a view on the IDS or alternative data space standards or models.

To do this, we developed a scoring methodology using a variety of technical and non-technical criteria that estimates how smoothly/quickly an organisation could move to a Technical Readiness Level of 8 for the identified IDS role, representing a functioning proof of concept and being more likely to be close to IDS Operational Certification. The services of these organisations were assessed against these criteria by interviewing representative stakeholders using a structured questionnaire, and the responses used to generate an overall ‘IDS Readiness Score’.

Our analyses of 13 different services across the industry against the IDS-RAM revealed that because the specification for the five IDS core services is highly specific, and as none of the services were developed with the IDS in mind, no services have a high alignment to any of the roles. This would mean that significant development efforts would be required for any service if it is to become certified and play a role in an IDS. While many organisations showed good alignment with the Metadata Broker role, primarily due to their services in facilitating the dissemination, discoverability and accessibility of Open Access books, only a few organisations were identified for other roles such as Vocabulary Providers and Identity Providers. Notably, no services were identified that could fulfil the roles of Clearing House or App Store Provider. This research also highlighted a general lack of IDS-compatible information security among organisations specialising in open data and a significant gap in knowledge about data spaces and IDS.

Based on the work conducted here, it is recommended to pursue the deployment of a single, well-administered IDS to support the exchange Open Access book usage and other scholarly outputs, emphasising simplicity, repeatability, and accountability. To address the identified gaps, we advise to partner with organisations possessing both IDS architectural knowledge and expertise in scholarly communications for data model development and technical roadmapping. Additionally, to bridge the knowledge gap and foster engagement, an education and outreach program targeting organisations within scholarly communications about the value and functionality of IDS is crucial. Exploring multiple paths for an IDS MVP, including using Data Space as a Service (DSaaS), building a data space

collaboratively within the scholarly communication sector, and organising an open innovation competition, could facilitate the effective implementation of IDS solutions tailored to the needs of the scholarly communications industry.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This report was developed for the OA Books Usage Data Trust (OAeBUDT) as part of their “Advancing to Launch by Developing IDS Governance Building Blocks” project. More information about this project can be found on the OAEBUDT website¹ and their Zenodo site².

We want to thank the organisations and the many individuals who donated their time during the interview, subsequent collection of any remaining information for the questionnaire, and review of the report. We recognise International Data Spaces are a new concept for many of those who talked to us, so their patience in understanding this new model and the project is much appreciated. We also want to thank Christina Drummond for engaging with us, and all members of the Mellon Project Advisory Board, Technical Advisory Committee and Board of Trustees for their time and valuable feedback throughout the project.

Lastly, thanks to Sonia Jimenez at the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) for the discussions on the IDS RAM and certification requirements, and to the IDSA for use of their data space image in this report.

This project was funded by the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation.

¹ <https://www.oabookusage.org/>

² <https://zenodo.org/communities/2022to2025-oa-book-usage-ids-governance-building-blocks?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

OAEBUDT AND AN OA BOOKS USAGE DATA SPACE

For the past eight years an international research effort has been developing and working towards the direct sovereign data exchange and benchmarking of open and proprietary usage data about Open Access (OA) books. The OA Book Usage Data Trust (OAeBUDT) was born out of this collaboration, and through funding from the Mellon Foundation and working with stakeholders, they have been documenting book metadata and impact reporting challenges, the book usage data supply chain, OA book usage data applications, and data governance frameworks³.

As part of their mission to ‘champion strategies for the improved publication and management of open-access books by exchanging reliable usage data in a trusted, equitable, and community-governed way’, a new effort is underway to develop an International Data Space (IDS) for Open Access books usage data. The goal of this IDS would be to deliver the exchange of trusted, scalable, cross-platform Open Access books usage data that is generated by commercial and public platforms and services.

In 2022 The Mellon Foundation awarded funds to OAEbUDT to focus on the development of “governance building blocks” to develop governance mechanisms, legal and participatory frameworks and a sustainability model for a minimum viable product (MVP) operational launch of an IDS in 2025. As part of this work, the OAEbUDT needs to understand what current platforms and services may be capable of providing the five core functional IDS network services to the OAEbUDT. These core services are the Identity Provider, Metadata Broker, IDS Clearing House, Vocabulary Provider, and App Store Provider. This project therefore assesses operational scholarly publishing service providers against these IDS core services described in the Reference Architecture Model 4.0⁴ and emerging certification specification documents. OAEbUDT's focus is on developing sustainable, open scholarly infrastructure that is compliant with POSI⁵, and as such, attributes about the service providers that might provide further insight towards technical sustainability have also been included in the analyses.

Results from this work will inform the next stages of technical work for the OAEbUDT, including: a) the development of the OAEbUDT IDS technical research and development roadmap, b) systems integration to support an MVP pilot of usage data exchange between two cohorts of <6 OA book usage data providers via IDS core service providers in the IDSA sandbox (2023-2025), and c) technical roadmap development to explore making the OAEbUDT IDS stack extensible to usage data for other scholarly outputs.

³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/oaebu?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

⁴ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/publications/ids-ram/>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.24343/C34W2H>

ROLES AND FUNCTION OF DATA SPACES

Introduction to data spaces

A data space is an integrated framework that brings together essential data infrastructures and governance systems to support the secure sharing of data between data providers and recipients. Within this framework, there is a secure and privacy-focused infrastructure that enables the pooling, accessing, sharing, processing, and utilisation of data. This is governed by a clear, practical, and fair structure, ensuring access to and use of data in a transparent, proportionate, and non-discriminatory manner, backed by trustworthy data governance mechanisms set by the data space operator.

IDS standard

The International Data Spaces Association (IDSA)⁶ has developed the International Data Space (IDS) standard (see image below) and published a Reference Architecture Model (RAM)⁷. This standard has a strong focus on interoperability, data sovereignty and certification at its core, creating trust amongst participants within the IDS. The IDS model is still in early stages of development; while all components have a specification published for them, only some have an actual standard. A handful of data spaces are live with many more planned⁸.

Figure 1: High level depiction of an IDSA data space. Image: International Data Spaces Association, accessed 24 January 2024; <https://internationaldataspaces.org/why/data-spaces/>. Used with permission from the IDSA.

⁶ <https://internationaldataspaces.org>

⁷ <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/v/ids-ram-4/>

⁸ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/adopt/data-spaces-radar/>

Connector

Organisations or individuals who wish to either provide or receive data through the IDS must operate a Connector as these allow the exchange of data via endpoints they expose. The Connector is one of the most critical components within IDS and must be certified as functioning correctly by an evaluation facility. A certificate is issued by the CA that can then be presented by the Connector to other Connectors for verification, which in turn establishes trust that they are both functioning correctly and securely. Whilst the Connector is integral to a functioning IDS, identification and examination of these are out of scope of this work.

Identity Provider

An Identity Provider provides the role of creating, maintaining, managing, monitoring, and validating identity information of and for participants in the IDS. This role is critical in ensuring the security of the IDS and to avoid unauthorised access to any data. Every participant in the IDS owns an identity (describing the participant) and uses an identity for authentication. The Identity Provider consists of three components: a Certification Authority (which manages and issues digital certificates for every participant), a Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS, managing the dynamic attributes of all participants via tokens), and the Participant Information Service (ParIS, which provides business-level information of participants to other requesting participants).

Metadata Broker

Metadata Brokers provide data providers with the ability to publish information about their data sources in terms of content, structure, quality, and currency, enabling other IDS participants in finding and understanding what data is available across the IDS. A Metadata Broker is not a message broker and does not distribute data assets by itself.

Clearing House

The main responsibility of the IDS Clearing House is to track and record who is using what data in the IDS. It is the clearing and settlement service for all data exchange and financial transactions within the IDS. It bases all its functions on a logging service that records information relevant for clearing and billing as well as usage control. It uses the data to provide a Clearing and Settlement Service on the basis of usage contracts and helps with the atomisation of payments between a Data Provider and a Data Consumer. It can also use this information to provide a Billing Service to allow the Data Space Operator the billing of the participants.

Vocabulary Provider

Vocabulary Providers helps data consumers understand the nature (e.g. schema) of the data they are consuming. They provide standardised descriptors for data based on accepted best practices. They are needed to provide a platform to host,

maintain, publish, and document the additional vocabularies. It provides endpoints to enable the seamless communication with IDS connectors and other infrastructure components.

App Store Provider

App Store Providers are responsible for supporting the searching and distribution of data applications that can be deployed in participants' IDS Connectors to execute tasks like transformation, aggregation or data analytics. The Store should provide an interface for publishing and retrieving apps as well the corresponding metadata.

IDSA certification requirements

To build trust between participants, the IDSA requires certain standards to be reached in terms of the operational environment, the actual infrastructure the software components are operated within and the components themselves. The Operational Environment Certification is based on and designed to have compatibility with ISO27001⁹, a respected global standard for information security management systems.

ASSIGNMENT AND SCOPE

67 Bricks was tasked to assess operational scholarly publishing service providers (at current Technical Readiness Levels 7-9) against the IDS core services described in the Reference Architecture Model 4.0¹⁰ and emerging certification specification documents for interconnected services. As the OAeBUDT have decided on the IDS as their model for implementation¹¹, 67 Bricks was asked to assess against only this model and was not asked to take a view on the IDS or alternative data space standards or models. Gap analysis was used to identify organisations and/or services in the OA book usage data ecosystem that might be able to perform IDS related functional roles, noting additional technical or organisational development that would be needed to meet certification and security requirements as described in the IDS technical Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM 4.0).

METHODOLOGY

Research plan

An industry and technology consultant from within 67 Bricks performed the audit and technical gap analysis and documented the results. The engagement began with initial desk research supported by a virtual kick-off meeting with key

⁹ https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDS-RAM_4_0/blob/main/documentation/4_Perspectives_of_the_Reference_Architecture_Model/4_2_Certification_Perspective/CertificationScheme/Operational-Environment-Certification.md

¹⁰ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/publications/ids-ram/>

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/8345034>

OAeBUDT stakeholders to ensure a joint understanding of the vision, goals and priorities of this piece of work. A research plan was produced, outlining the approach and methodologies to be used for this analysis, and feedback received from OAeBUDT on the plan.

Information gathering

The primary methods used during the course of the engagement were desk research of publicly available information on various organisations and structured interviews. The initial desk research provided the foundational information on which organisations to contact. Organisations identified through desk research and internal 67 Bricks collective industry knowledge to be interviewed were discussed and reviewed with Christina Drummond and the Board of Trustees. The aim of the interviews was to gather more detailed technical and operational information about the organisation and services under consideration that could not be obtained from the desk research alone (i.e. from internal collective 67 Bricks expertise or reviewing publicly available information).

We have provided below an outline of what was developed and included for the interviews. A template of the structured questionnaire used in the interviews is included in the Appendix.

Non-technical criteria

A number of organisational criteria were assessed to provide a broader context for which the technical criteria can be considered. This included:

- **Country of legal incorporation** - Which country the organisation is legally incorporated in.
- **Countries serviced** - List of countries / world regions the organisation currently operates within.
- **Country of data processing** - Which countries the organisation actually stores / processes data within. This can influence issues around data sharing (e.g. between EU and US based organisations), which in turn impacts the roles they are best suited to.
- **Currently supported content types** - e.g. closed books, open data, journal articles etc.
- **Staffing** - Is the organisation primarily run by volunteers, staffed part or full time?
- **Governance model** - whether the organisation is commercial, not for profit or public. Definitions (for the purpose of this work) are:
 - **Commercial** - includes corporations, LLCs, partnerships, sole proprietorships, where there is direct financial reward or incentive for the owning/governing individuals in the financial success of the organisation.
 - **Not for profit** - has a charitable, educational, religious, or scientific purpose and any financial surplus is re-invested into the organisation's mission, not individuals or shareholders.
 - **Public** - managed by a government agency and typically funded by a government body or taxation. Any financial surplus is typically re-invested into the organisation's mission, not individuals or shareholders.

- Age - Is the organisation less than 1 year old, less than 2 years old, less than 10 years old or greater than 10 (SCOSS requires minimum 2 years to be eligible¹²)? Older organisations are more likely to continue existing; though they may have more technical debt and be less able to innovate than younger organisations.

Technical criteria

67 Bricks organised a meeting with IDSA to understand at a deeper level the requirements around certification and the IDS-RAM. We used the discussions with IDSA and publicly available catalogues¹³ and RAM¹⁴ to develop a questionnaire (using a combination of qualitative and quantitative assessments) to work through with potential partners in a systematic, unbiased approach. The majority of the technical questions were based on factors required for Operational Environment Certification¹⁵ and to identify a suitable Technical Readiness Level and draw attention to any gaps in relation to this. The full questionnaire can be found in the Appendix.

If organisations indicated during the interview that they had been involved in any IDS development, we would analyse the individual APIs and documentation of the service(s). However, because the requirements of IDSA roles are very specific to their implementation, and as no organisations indicated involvement or development in an IDS data space, we concluded that no organisations would have developed sufficiently against this to warrant a full analysis of their APIs and documentation.

IDS Readiness Scoring criteria

The scope of the work was to assess and include the Technical Readiness Levels (TRL)¹⁶ of existing organisations for playing a core role in an IDS data space and to understand how close they are to IDS Operational Environment certification. Although all services considered here are fully operational and are therefore all TRL of 9 for their own service, using standard Technical Readiness Levels were not as useful. This is because almost all organisations had little awareness or understanding of International Data Spaces, and none had made active choices towards development or certification, thus putting them all at a TRL of 0 to 1 for a role in an IDSA data space. As such, we created a scoring methodology that tries to estimate how smoothly/quickly an organisation could move to a readiness level of 8 for the identified IDS role, representing a functioning proof of concept and being more likely to be close to operational certification. We have termed this the 'IDS Readiness (IDSR) Score'.

¹² <https://scoss.org/how-it-works/application-process/>

¹³ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/publications/most-important-documents/>

¹⁴ https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDS-RAM_4_0/tree/main/documentation/4_Perspectives_of_the_Reference_Architecture_Model/4_2_Certification_Perspective/CertificationScheme

¹⁵ https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDS-RAM_4_0/blob/main/documentation/4_Perspectives_of_the_Reference_Architecture_Model/4_2_Certification_Perspective/CertificationScheme/Operational-Environment-Certification.md

¹⁶ Horizon 2020 work programme 2014 – 2015 (19. General Annexes Revised); https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal4/doc/call/h2020/common/1617621-part_19_general_annexes_v.2.0_en.pdf

To help reach a score for each organisation and aid comparisons we have identified the following pillars based on technical and non-technical criteria detailed in the Methodology section. Each pillar is considered for each organisation (or service), leading to a total IDS Readiness Score, calculated as a weighted average of each section. The overall IDSR Score can be between High and Low, and each score represents the following:

High: High technical readiness and closest to IDS operational certification, able to start building and hosting an IDS service with no additional R&D.

Medium-high: Minor gaps present, judged to require less effort to close (effort as a combination of time, resources and expertise).

Medium: Few major gaps or many minor gaps that require effort to close.

Medium-low: Major gaps in several areas requiring substantial effort to close.

Low: Lowest readiness level and far from IDS operational certification, requiring an overwhelming effort to be ready or represents a fundamental organisational incompatibility.

Where organisations were unable to provide an answer to a question, this influences the score. We have noted that they were unsure, but for the sake of scoring, we assumed a response that would correspond with the lowest score.

IDS Readiness Scoring implications

It is worth stressing that the IDSR Scores calculated and presented here for each organisation and service are only to serve as an estimate of how smoothly/quickly an organisation might be able to move to a readiness level of 8 for the identified service within an IDS. Scores should not be used to infer anything other than this. All organisations (and associated services) were included in this analysis because they are respected organisations within the industry. Each IDS Readiness Score refers only to this work, and any 'lower' scores do not indicate any wider problems or poor management of those organisations.

IDS-compatible information security (20%)

What cybersecurity measures are in place, including whether the organisation has achieved ISO27001 certification. The operational certification process for IDS is based closely on ISO27001, so any organisation having already achieved this is desirable. Similar infosec certification would also score well here. IDS typically operate through HTTP APIs. This value has been given a higher weighting because achieving ISO27001 certification for an SME (Small and Medium-sized Enterprise) with no prior consideration of doing so will often require a project of 12-18 months driven from a leadership level to reach. This section only assessed and scored for IDS-compatible information security, and does not reflect any other information security the organisation may have.

High: Already achieved any level of IDS certification

Medium-high: Achieved ISO27001 or similar certification.

Medium: In process of achieving IDS, ISO27001 or similar certification.

Medium-low: No formal certification, but has implemented reasonable IDS-compatible infosec controls.

Low: No formal certification and limited IDS-compatible infosec controls implemented. This score does not suggest that the organisation does not have any infosec but only that it is not an IDS-compatible form.

Existing experience and alignment with IDS (20%)

How much experience with and alignment to the IDS roles does the service have. A high alignment score would suggest that the organisation and service could easily be adapted to fulfil that role.

Already having experience with IDS would be desirable and would indicate that the organisation and service could be more easily adapted to IDS. This section gains a weighting of 20% as gaining that expertise either by developing in-house capabilities or buying in expertise will require effort.

High: Has a production service for one of the IDS roles.

Medium-high: Has a prototype that is specifically aimed at being an IDS service.

Medium: Has started to consider how an existing production service could be adapted to be IDS-compatible.

Medium-low: Has a production service that has similarities with the identified IDS service but was not specifically designed to operate within one.

Low: Has a production service that has little to no compatibility with a data space service.

Infrastructure (15%)

Currently, HTTPS is the main communication method underlying IDS (though may extend to others in the future), as such suitable services would have experience hosting web services in a secure and reliable manner. They would have secure APIs with well architected networks designed to limit the potential damage of DDoS and unauthorised access. They would securely track changes to infrastructure and record thorough audit trails of their systems.

IDS makes little specifications as to the actual technologies used, while there are building blocks that could be used to deliver parts of a service, there is no expectation that they must be used. The IDS-RAM is a flexible and adaptable framework. The IDS testbed¹⁷, for helping organisations prove the correctness of their components with already validated open source components, utilises Docker.

Cloud hosting services operate with a shared responsibility model, it isn't enough to just use AWS or Azure, an organisation needs to employ specific services such as AWS WAF (Web Application Firewall) to appropriately protect services in alignment with the relevant well architected frameworks.

¹⁷ <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDS-testbed>

A point is awarded for each of the following:

- Provides public HTTP APIs
- Has distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) mitigations in place for public APIs
- Has sensible precautions in place to detect and limit network intrusions (e.g. firewall rules and intrusion detection systems)
- Maintains audit trails of systems
- Has a defined service level agreement (SLA) in place

Global presence and operations (10%)

This section aims to evaluate the suitability of an organisation and the service based on the geographies it operates in. The OAeBUDT-IDS has to be EU compliant, so ideally the service would already be operating within the EU. It is expected that users of the IDS will be a global audience.

High: Service serves a global market and is active in a large proportion of countries both within the US, EU and rest of the world. The service is operated from within the EU.

Medium-high: Serves a number of countries and aims to expand to global markets and is operated in a EU compatible way.

Medium: Targets a handful of countries and is EU compatible.

Medium-low: Targets a single country outside of the EU but has ambition to expand to more.

Low: Targets a single country outside of the EU with no ambition to expand and is not EU compatible.

Data management (10%)

A point is awarded for each of the following:

- Has any policies or guidelines relating to the curation and quality of data sets.
- Uses authentication to ensure changes to data sets are controlled.
- Maintains an audit trail of changes to data sets.
- Has rules around personally identifiable information (PII)/GDPR where relevant (or purposefully avoid PII).
- Self-descriptive APIs

Software development capabilities & sustainability (15%)

How likely the organisation is going to be around and be able to build, maintain and support the service in the medium to long term. Ideal organisations would have their software available through an open source licence to ensure long term sustainability and ideally operate under POSI¹⁸. A strong development capability is preferred as this ensures the team can create and manage an IDS service, which is very likely to be new to these organisations.

¹⁸ <https://openscholarlyinfrastructure.org>

High: Has a stable development capability, has defined policies around software development practices and a quality assurance strategy in place

Medium: Has a semi-stable development capability, has no formal policies around software development practices

Low: Has unstable development capabilities, no policies around quality or practices

Standards (10%)

Includes the ability to develop and influence the standards-making process. IDS is still an emerging standard, undergoing large changes (such as development of the IDS protocol) on the road to stabilisation. Any organisation trying to operate a service within an IDS needs to take an interest in the development and applying updates of standards to their own systems.

Keeping an eye on standards development is considered to take a smaller amount of effort than some other criteria identified, thus this section is only given a 10% weighting.

High: Takes an active part in defining standards and update their systems to reflect changes in standards they are targeting

Medium: Takes some part in definition standards or sitting on working groups or actively pursues adhesion to a set standard

Low: Takes no part in defining standards or sitting on any working groups

ANALYSES

Identity Providers

EZproxy, OCLC

IDS Readiness Score: **Medium**

EZproxy¹⁹ was identified as a potential Identity Provider role as it has some alignment due to their management of certificates for authentication purposes. It is the only service identified for this role that has achieved ISO27001, making it the service with the highest IDS Readiness Score for the Identity Provider role.

¹⁹ <https://www.oclc.org/en/ezproxy.html>

OCLC²⁰ is a large not-for-profit organisation that provides many shared technology services, original research, and community programs for its membership and the library community. It fulfils many of the criteria under POSI's governance and sustainability requirements, although none of their services are open source or data is open.

Criteria	IDSR Score	Discussion
IDS information security compatibility*	Medium-high	Has ISO27001, SOC2 and many other formal qualifications ²¹
Existing expertise and alignment	Medium-low	EZproxy has some alignment with the Identity Provider role due to their management of certificates for authentication purposes. They claim to have some experience with building wider data spaces but not specifically IDS.
Infrastructure	High	Has DDoS mitigations and robust network security with firewall and network intrusion systems. Maintains audit trails and an SLA of 24/7 with no known failures to maintain that SLA.
Global presence	High	Founded in the USA. The OCLC has a global presence including North America, Asia and Europe
Data management	Medium	Has no API and limited data sets that are actively managed by EZproxy (as it isn't responsible for handling data). Audit trails are maintained and GDPR/PII protections are implemented where needed.
Software development & sustainability	Medium-high	Has a large technical team ~800 full time employed staff. Follows numerous standards around security, though none mentioned around quality. Has cooperated with numerous organisations to build shared services.
Standards	Medium	Involved in the creation of several standards through NISO such as Dublin Core. Are not subjected to standards they themselves haven't defined outside of infosec.

*This section only assessed and scored for IDS-compatible information security and does not reflect any other information security the organisation may have.

²⁰ <https://www.oclc.org/en/home.html>

²¹ <https://www.oclc.org/en/trust/compliance.html#trust-certifications>

Identity and Access, LibLynxIDS Readiness Score: **Medium-low**

Identity and Access solutions²² provided by LibLynx were identified as potentially fulfilling the role of an Identity Provider because it can provide secure authentication and access to users across multiple products. Our research found that the service does indeed have a fairly good alignment with an Identity Provider, especially so as it manages X.509 certificates, however its lack of ISO27001 (or similar) certification and LibLynx having no experience with any form of data space are the main reasons for this service not receiving a higher IDS Readiness Score. The host organisation, LibLynx²³, is a well-established (founded 2014) commercial organisation that offers a variety of services across identity, access and analytics for publishers, libraries and other services providers. Other factors worth noting are that one of their other services (COUNTER Reporting²⁴) provides revenue-generating services that leverage COUNTER metrics, and they fulfil very few of the POSI criteria (likely due to the commercial nature of the organisation).

Criteria	IDSR Score	Discussion
IDSR information security compatibility*	Low	Has no infosec certification
Existing expertise and alignment	Medium-low	Has not built anything aligned with IDS. The service does manage X.509 certificates for integrating with SAML and provides authentication services for other applications which are key requirements for an Identity Provider.
Infrastructure	High	The service is deployed on the Digital Ocean cloud and makes use of Docker. LibLynx provides a 99.9% uptime SLA with no incidents in the past 3 years. Audit trail maintained and access logs kept. Firewalls and DDoS mitigations in place to protect public facing HTTPS API.
Global presence	High	Founded in Virginia, USA. The Identity and Access Service has global reach. It operates from servers in the USA, UK and The Netherlands.
Data management	Medium	The API is not self-descriptive, but does have documentation. Approximately 2TB of data handled. It does handle PII and has been designed to comply with GDPR requirements. Authentication is required to modify data.

²² <https://www.liblynx.com/publishers/identity-access-solutions/>

²³ <https://www.liblynx.com>

²⁴ <https://www.liblynx.com/publishers/counter-reporting/>

Software development & sustainability	Medium	Primarily uses employed staff, with 5 out of 14 in technical roles. Has developed services in conjunction with PSI Metrics. Has no formal policy around software development.
Standards	Medium	Has members on several working groups including COUNTER, OA Switchboard, Seamless Access and Research Identity. The system conforms to COUNTER and Seamless Access standards, but none that LibLynx doesn't have some influence over.

*This section only assessed and scored for IDS-compatible information security and does not reflect any other information security the organisation may have.

TheIPregistry.org, PSI

IDS Readiness Score: **Low**

TheIPregistry.org²⁵ was identified as potentially filling the role of an Identity Provider because it is a well-established method of automatic IP authentication and dissemination via APIs. Our analysis revealed that PSI outsources their software development, has not been actively involved in developing any standards, and due to the limited information we were able to obtain about the infrastructure and the service, it has received the lowest score under the Identity Provider role. PSI²⁶ is a small commercial organisation that enables libraries, publishers and membership societies to access scholarly content, leveraging IP data as one of the key underlying mechanisms. Like many of the other organisations assessed, they do not follow the POSI principles.

Criteria	IDSR Score	Discussion
IDS information security compatibility*	Low	Has no formal infosec certification.
Existing experience and alignment	Low**	The service has some alignment. It does store additional metadata about the IP addresses it contains around organisations that use them which is similar to some limited aspects of the Identity Provider role. Unable to answer relevant questions about alignment with the Identity Provider role.
Infrastructure	Medium-Low**	Limited information available from interviews, the organisation relies on outsourced developers to handle building and operating the service. Though has an SLA and maintains an audit trail.

²⁵ <https://www.psiregistry.org/theipregistry>

²⁶ <https://www.psiregistry.org/>

Global presence	Medium -high	Incorporated in the UK. The IP Registry serves a global market, including the EU, with data processing occurring within the UK.
Data management	Medium -high	Has a self-descriptive API, has to respect policies around GDPR/PII but no policies on data quality. Maintains an audit trail of changes to data.
Software development & sustainability	Medium -low	No policies around software quality, uses a third-party to provide software development and thus has no technical staff within the organisation.
Standards	Low	Takes no part in defining standards nor subjected to any standards.

*This section only assessed and scored for IDS-compatible information security and does not reflect any other information security the organisation may have.

**Respondent was unable to answer multiple questions for these, so the lowest score was applied.

Metadata Brokers

IA Scholar (formerly FatCat), Internet Archive

IDS Readiness Score: **Medium**

Internet Archive (IA) Scholar²⁷ was identified as potentially providing a role as a Metadata Broker because it indexes and provides a means to search numerous scholarly content types. With a relatively close alignment to a Metadata Broker, high infosec in place, a large technical team, clear procedures in data management and having actively taken part in developing standards, it received the highest IDS Readiness Score in the Metadata Broker category. The parent organisation, Internet Archive²⁸, is a mid-sized non-profit organisation that is creating a digital library of Internet sites and other cultural artefacts in digital form, providing free access to researchers, historians, scholars, people with print disabilities, and the general public. Their mission is to provide universal access to all knowledge. IA Scholar (FatCat)²⁹ has also been the recipient of previous Mellon Foundations Grants as part of long-trail Open Access journal preservation, and their service is open source, aligning more closely with some aspects of POSI.

Criteria	IDSR Score	Discussion
IDS information security compatibility*	Medium	Has started the process to achieve FedRAMP (similar to SOC2, specific for the USA).

²⁷ <https://scholar.archive.org/>

²⁸ <https://archive.org/>

²⁹ <https://fatcat.wiki/about>

Existing experience and alignment	Medium -low	Service stores data and metadata about academic articles and provides a means to search over them, integrating with numerous sources to populate. Does aim to follow some guidance around data spaces, but not specifically IDS.
Infrastructure	High	Operates on their own data centres, has DDoS mitigations in place and suitable network security. Audit trails are maintained and there is an SLA for some value-adding services. Docker is used for deploying some services.
Global presence	Medium -high	Global presence, with data handling happening in the USA.
Data management	High	200TB of data managed over 200M items. Makes use of JATS, MARC & Dublin Core. Has procedures relating to data management, authentication is required for changing metadata, maintains audit trails around changes to data. They actively avoid PII as their data sets are public and make use of OpenAPI to describe APIs.
Software development & sustainability	High	Has a large technical team, ~50-60% of 150 FTE employees.
Standards	High	Has actively developed several ISO standards around data archival and exchange. Makes use of several format standards they were not involved in creating.

*This section only assessed and scored for IDS-compatible information security and does not reflect any other information security the organisation may have.

Metadata Plus, Crossref

IDS Readiness Score: **Medium**

Crossref Metadata Plus service³⁰ was identified as a potential Metadata Broker because of the vast network of linking it provides across the scholarly industry for many outputs. Scoring highly for infosec, global presence and having a strong alignment to the Metadata Broker, this service scored relatively well overall in this category. Crossref³¹ is a mid-sized, well established not for profit organisation that exists to make scholarly communications better by making research objects easy to find, cite, link, assess, and reuse. They have signed up to POSI³² so are striving towards this, and their code is open source³³.

³⁰ <https://www.crossref.org/services/metadata-retrieval/metadata-plus/>

³¹ <https://www.crossref.org/>

³² <https://www.crossref.org/blog/crossrefs-board-votes-to-adopt-the-principles-of-open-scholarly-infrastructure/>

³³ <https://gitlab.com/crossref/>

Criteria	IDSR Score	Discussion
IDS information security compatibility*	Medium-high	Has achieved SOC2 (a US based standard, akin to ISO27001) which demonstrates care in securing data along with regular pentests.
Existing expertise and alignment	Medium-low	No experience with IDS but the service has linking to other data sources, manages book metadata and provides a means to query it via UI and API, giving it a fairly strong alignment with the Metadata Broker service.
Infrastructure	Medium-high	The public HTTPS API is defended against DDoS and has firewalls in place. The service has a defined SLA in place. Uses Docker for some things via Kubernetes orchestration.
Global presence	High	The service has global reach and has active users in many countries
Data management	Medium	Self-descriptive API but minimal standards for data quality. Authentication is optional in some cases; this can mean data integrity is at risk. Successfully manages over 140 million records (~185Gb).
Software development & sustainability	Medium-high	Has a good sized technical team (18) that make up 40% of all staff employed. Has no quality strategy / policies in place and has co-operated with DataCite to develop a shared service.
Standards	Medium	It took a key role in defining JATS standard but isn't subjected to any standards they did not have a role in defining.

*This section only assessed and scored for IDS-compatible information security and does not reflect any other information security the organisation may have.

Registry of OpenAIRE Graph, OpenAIRE

IDS Readiness Score: **Medium**

The registry underlying OpenAIRE Graph³⁴ was identified as being considered for the role of Metadata Broker because it is a vast aggregator of millions of metadata records collected from trusted data sources (with the OpenAIRE Provide³⁵ as the interface to access the data source registry). The registry scored the highest in this category for existing experience and alignment with data spaces as it is part of the European Open

³⁴ <https://catalogue.openaire.eu/service/openaire.graph/overview>

³⁵ <https://provide.openaire.eu/home>

Science Cloud, which could be viewed as a form of data space, it has been active in both shaping standards and following other standards, and has good systems in place for monitoring and prevention of DDoS attacks. The main area where it is furthest from IDS operational certification is that it has not achieved (or progressing towards) any form of recognised infosec certification. The host organisation, OpenAIRE³⁶ (AMKE), is a non-profit organisation with a mission to promote open scholarship and improve discoverability, accessibility, shareability, reusability, reproducibility, and monitoring of data-driven research results, globally. It does this by operating a European e-infrastructure offering a diverse set of public services. OpenAIRE is committed to POSI³⁷ and their code is open source.

Criteria	IDSR Score	Discussion
IDS information security compatibility*	Low	Has not achieved ISO27001 or similar certifications
Existing expertise and alignment	Medium	OpenAIRE is part of the European Open Science Cloud ³⁸ , which could be viewed as a form of data space. Doesn't use any certificates for authentication. The service has some alignment with the Metadata Broker, providing a means of querying over book metadata, linking out to other services. Although it doesn't provide a public API that can be queried, only a UI.
Infrastructure	High	The system is primarily deployed within OpenAIRE's own data centre, but can be scaled into cloud. Has a 99.5% uptime SLA in place (which has been kept the past 3 years). Audit trail maintained. Defences against DDoS attacks and firewalls are in place. Aligned with POSI. Some services make use of Docker.
Global presence	High	Organisation is based in Greece. Data centres are in Poland. A global market served.
Data management	Medium-high	The service manages data in various formats, such as OpenAIRE's internal format, Dublin Core, DataCite, JATS & DCAT. Approximately 900 TB in total. The OpenAIRE graph has Swagger available. PII data about users is processed in accordance with GDPR. Audit trails of changes are maintained.

³⁶ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

³⁷ <https://www.openaire.eu/principles-open-scholarly-infrastructure-openaire-assessment>

³⁸ <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

Software development & sustainability	Medium	Approximately 20 out of 25 staff are technical. There are no internal policies for software quality.
Standards	High	Taken part in defining the Scholix ³⁹ standard. Follows numerous standards around data formats they were not involved in.

*This section only assessed and scored for IDS-compatible information security and does not reflect any other information security the organisation may have.

DataCite Commons, DataCite IDS Readiness Score: **Medium**

DataCite Commons⁴⁰ was identified as being a potential Metadata Broker as it provides the ability to search a PID graph of publications, datasets, people and research organisations, and their connections. Whilst DataCommons performed highly on global presence, data management and software development, its lack of infosec certification was the major reason it does not receive a high overall score. DataCite⁴¹ is a small not-for-profit organisation that makes research more effective with metadata by supporting the creation and management of persistent identifiers (PIDs), integrating services to improve research workflows, and facilitating the discovery and reuse of research outputs and resources. DataCite is committed to POSI⁴² and their code is open source⁴³.

Criteria	IDSR Score	Discussion
IDS information security compatibility*	Low	No infosec certifications
Existing expertise and alignment	Medium -low	The service stores and searches over a variety of research outputs which provides a suitable alignment with the Metadata Broker. However, DataCite has never considered this in the context of IDS.
Infrastructure	Medium -high	The service uses GraphQL to provide an HTTPS API, and has DDoS and firewalls in place. Audit trails are maintained but no SLA is defined.
Global presence	High	Organisation is based in Germany while the service is operated within Ireland. It serves users globally.

³⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/1120265>

⁴⁰ <https://commons.datacite.org>

⁴¹ <https://datacite.org/>

⁴² <https://datacite.org/blog/our-commitment-to-posi/>

⁴³ <https://github.com/datacite>

Data management	High	Authentication via ORCID is required to modify data, an audit trail is maintained and GDPR is followed where needed. The API is self-describing ⁴⁴ . There are automated jobs that validate the quality of provided data.
Software development & sustainability	Medium-high	11 employees out of 28 are engineers. A lot of their software is open source ⁴⁵ , showing that they use automated workflows and testing practices. They have no explicit quality assurance policies.
Standards	Medium	Has taken part in defining standards around DOI, COUNTER, RAIR and CRediT. Service does not obey any standards not defined by themselves.

*This section only assessed and scored for IDS-compatible information security and does not reflect any other information security the organisation may have.

Thoth

IDS Readiness Score: **Medium**

Thoth is an open metadata management and dissemination platform and was identified as a potential Metadata Broker because it supports the creation and curation of high-quality metadata of OA books as a key part of its offering, with a catalogue search interface. Whilst it has reasonable alignment with the Metadata Broker, and has a strong global presence and good data management, it has no infosec certification, limiting its overall readiness towards certification in an IDS. Named after its only service, Thoth⁴⁶ is a small not-for-profit organisation (community interest company). Whilst they have not formally committed to POSI and so do not fulfil many of the criteria, they do align with POSI's commitment to be open source⁴⁷ and have open data.

Criteria	IDSR Score	Discussion
IDS information security compatibility*	Low	Has no formal infosec certification
Existing expertise and alignment	Medium-low	The service has reasonable alignment with the Metadata Broker, handling data in Onix, Marc and other formats. It integrates with a number of other services including DSpace, Open Book Collective and OAPEN with others being developed. It also has an API and GraphQL endpoint which allow flexible querying of data.

⁴⁴ <https://api.datacite.org/graphql>

⁴⁵ <https://github.com/datacite>

⁴⁶ <https://thoth.pub/>

⁴⁷ <https://github.com/thoth-pub>

Infrastructure	High	Has a public GraphQL HTTPS API with basic network security in place alongside an audit trail. Has some DDoS mitigation in place and there is no defined SLA. Alignment with POSI.
Global presence	High	Organisation is founded in the UK. Operates globally from Ireland.
Data management	Medium-high	Has both Swagger and GraphQL endpoints self-describing. Records updates to data and uses access control to restrict ability to modify data. Has no policies or guidelines around data quality but does respect PII/GDPR where needed
Software development & sustainability	Medium	Thoth is open source ⁴⁸ software and primarily uses Rust. The team is ~6 FTEs worth of employed staff, of that, 2.5 FTEs are technical. There is no quality assurance strategy in place and they have not cooperated with another organisation on building a shared service but have a collaboration with Open book Collective ⁴⁹ .
Standards	Medium	Takes no part in influencing any standards. Does follow numerous standards around schemas used, such as ONIX, MARC21, JSON, KBART, BibTeX and CSV.

*This section only assessed and scored for IDS-compatible information security and does not reflect any other information security the organisation may have.

OA Switchboard

IDS Readiness Score: **Medium-low**

OA Switchboard is a small not-for-profit organisation that enables publishers, academic institutions, and research funders to seamlessly communicate information about open access publications. Whilst they have sound infrastructure, good software development processes in place and have a global presence, their service is less in line with the Metadata Broker role and they have no formal infosec certifications. OA Switchboard is committed to POSI⁵⁰ and provide much of their code as open source⁵¹ (where legally possible).

Criteria	IDSR Score	Discussion
IDS information security compatibility*	Low	Has no formal infosec certification.

⁴⁸ <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth>

⁴⁹ <https://openbookcollective.org/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.oaswitchboard.org/posi7oct2021>

⁵¹ <https://bitbucket.org/oaswitchboard/api/src/master/>

Existing expertise and alignment	Low	The OA Switchboard service provides linking to other data sources but doesn't index book metadata. The service acts more like a router to direct requests to the right endpoint rather than serve responses itself. This means it is less aligned with the Metadata Broker role.
Infrastructure	Medium-high	Service has DDoS mitigations and sensibly secures the network in line with AWS best practices. The system is based on PaaS deployment with lambdas and doesn't use Docker. An incomplete audit trail is present (not everything is logged) and it has a defined SLA.
Global presence	High	The service is global with the main data processing handled within EU/Ireland.
Data management	Medium	The service doesn't manage much data as it is more of a message router, passing requests on to another source. Authentication is in place and an audit trail is available. Rules around GDPR are required and enforced. The API is not self-descriptive.
Software development & sustainability	High	Small team of 4, most of whom are technical in their role. There are rigorous policies on code checking and security in place.
Standards	Medium	Some involvement in early stages of standards development but hasn't been involved in any published standard.

*This section only assessed and scored for IDS-compatible information security and does not reflect any other information security the organisation may have.

OAeBU Workflows, COKI

IDS Readiness Score: **Medium-low**

The OAeBU Workflows was identified as having potential alignment with the Metadata Broker due to COKI's and the project's direct involvement in the Developing a Pilot Data Trust for Open Access Ebook Usage project⁵². However, after further analysis, it is not a clear fit for the Metadata Broker role, but could instead be seen as complementary to the proposed IDS by helping provide a means of transforming data into a common format, such as a data intermediary might. COKI (Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative) is a strategic initiative of Curtin University, which is a commercial organisation. COKI seeks to be the world's leading hub for analysis and evaluation of Open Knowledge in higher education. They do this by using the Observatory Platform and various workflows (Academic Observatory Workflows and Book Usage Workflows) to provide data products to partners.

⁵² <https://openknowledge.community/projects/book-usage-data-workflows/>

Criteria	IDSR Score	Discussion
IDS information security compatibility*	Low	Has no certification themselves and no plans to obtain any. They feel the size of their organisation to be a blocker to this.
Existing expertise and alignment	Low	The Observatory platform and specifically the OAeBU Workflows are about processing and transforming data over maintaining an index of what data is available where. This makes it a poor fit for the Metadata Broker role.
Infrastructure	Medium	Interviewees could not confirm that measures are in place to defend against DDoS attacks. The deployment does make use of Docker. There is basic firewall protection in place alongside an audit trail of activity. There is no defined SLA.
Global presence	Medium-high	Has users in North America, Australia and parts of Europe with data processing happening in the USA.
Data management	Medium	No policies relating to quality of data. Authentication is in place and audit trails of changes are available. They respect Australian rules around PII that fall short of EU GDPR regulations. The service does not have any self-descriptive APIs.
Software development & sustainability	Medium	Has a team of 6 technical staff out of 8 FTEs. There is no formal quality policy around software development but the software is open source so it is possible to see good practices around testing and automation are in place.
Standards	High	Has had some input in standards development (e.g. ROR) and follows standards around ONIX and COUNTER

*This section only assessed and scored for IDS-compatible information security and does not reflect any other information security the organisation may have.

Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB), OAPEN

IDS Readiness Score: **Medium-low**

Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB) is a discovery service that indexes and provides access to scholarly, peer-reviewed open access books. DOAB was identified as a potential Metadata Broker as it enables libraries and aggregators to use the metadata of all available titles in the DOAB and links out to these data. Whilst it aligns fairly well with the Metadata

Broker role and has a global presence, it has limited info sec, and the infrastructure and data management are not as sufficiently developed to make it anyway close to operational certification for an IDS. The host organisation, OAPEN⁵³, is a small not-for-profit organisation that is dedicated to open access, peer-reviewed books, and it provides three platforms as part of their goals to build a branded collection of Open Access peer-reviewed titles, increase the visibility and retrievability of high-quality publications, and to promote Open Access book publishing. OAPEN are committed to POSI and endorsed by SCOSS⁵⁴, and DOAB makes use of DSpace which is also endorsed by SCOSS⁵⁵.

Criteria	IDSR Score	Discussion
IDS information security compatibility*	Low	Has no infosec certification
Existing expertise and alignment	Medium-low	No experience with IDS. The service does index book metadata via ONIX and MARC21 formats. It links out to other services and has both a public API and UI.
Infrastructure	Medium-low**	There is no defined SLA in place. The API is not self-descriptive, but is documented. A partial audit trail is maintained. Use Cloudflare to prevent DDoS attacks. Deployed on AWS and makes use of Docker.
Global presence	High	Founded in The Netherlands. Serves a global market. Dspace is hosted and maintained by a Belgian firm using AWS eu-central-1 region (Frankfurt).
Data management	Medium-low	DOAB manages approximately 78k metadata records, (~180MB of data), OAPEN manages approx. 31k full text records. There is no authentication required to access data, but is required to modify data. No audit trail of data changes is kept. No PII is maintained in the data sets (though login data for publishers is maintained in accordance with GDPR).
Software development & sustainability	Medium	4 out of 10 full time staff are technical. Has worked with other organisations in developing a shared service with OPERAS-P, OPERAS-D and COKI. Has no defined software quality strategy.

⁵³ <https://www.oapen.org/>

⁵⁴ <https://scoss.org/what-is-scoss/scossfamily/>

⁵⁵ <https://scoss.org/what-is-scoss/defining-open-infrastructure/>

Standards	Medium	Has taken no role in developing standards. Does make use of standards for some data formats.
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*This section only assessed and scored for IDS-compatible information security and does not reflect any other information security the organisation may have.

**Respondent was unable to answer question SS6 so the lowest score was applied for this.

Vocabulary Providers

ROR

IDS Readiness Score: **Medium-low**

ROR (Research Organization Registry) serves as a registry of open persistent identifiers for research organisations and was identified as a Vocabulary Provider as it provides a standardised descriptor for organisations' names based on accepted best practices. However, as it does not actually manage ontologies or store book metadata, it does not have a high alignment with a Vocabulary Provider in an IDS. Whilst it has infrastructure that aligns more towards an IDS and software development processes and data management that might support this, the lack of formal infosec and alignment are the key reasons it may be fairly far from operational certification. ROR is a small not for profit global initiative by California Digital Library, Crossref, and DataCite which collectively assume and share responsibility for ROR governance, operations, resourcing, and decision-making under a Memorandum of Agreement⁵⁶ (and therefore has no legal entity). ROR is endorsed by SCOSS⁵⁷ and aligned with POSI.

Criteria	IDSR Score	Discussion
IDS information security compatibility*	Low	No infosec certifications.
Existing expertise and alignment	Low	Never build a proof of concept for IDS. Does not actively store book metadata and does not manage ontologies.
Infrastructure	Medium-high	Deployed on AWS via Github actions and Docker. There is no defined SLA for the service (though it has only had one known 10 minute outage in 3 years). There are no access control decision logs (as there are no such decisions), but there are some audit logs stored. AWS WAF is used to protect the public API from DDoS attacks with the application appropriately secured within its VPC.

⁵⁶ <https://ror.org/documents/ROR-Memorandum-of-Agreement-2022.pdf>

⁵⁷ <https://scoss.org/what-is-scoss/defining-open-infrastructure/>

Global presence	High	ROR is an initiative driven by DataCite (Germany), California Digital Library (USA) & Crossref (USA). It is not a separately incorporated entity. Has users in over 200 countries, making it serve a global user base. The service makes use of AWS services based in Ireland.
Data management	Medium	Has guidelines for data ⁵⁸ . Dataset contains over 107,000 records (~31MB zipped). The API is not self-descriptive. There is no access control to the services offered by ROR. Activity avoids PII.
Software development & sustainability	High	Team consists of 4 full time and 2 part time with 1-2 as technical staff. Has defined developer guidelines ⁵⁹ .
Standards	Medium	Active in a NISO working group, does not follow other standards.

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Submit, Retrieve, Reuse, ISSN IC

IDS Readiness Score: **Medium-low**

Submit, Retrieve, Reuse⁶⁰ service was identified as potentially fulfilling the role of the Vocabulary Provider because it provides a way to search and validate ISSN in an organisation's database by comparing their data to the ISSN Register, and to retrieve core ISSN metadata from the Keepers Registry, ROAD and other indexing services. Analysis revealed that whilst it has an ontology and managed ontologies of the data within it, it does not offer a SPARQL method of querying data that Vocabulary Providers typically require, lacks a public API and limited infrastructure capabilities that an IDS might require. It is on the path to achieving ISO27001 certification, which is a significant step towards operational certification. ISSN IC (International Standard Serial Number International Centre)⁶¹, which hosts Submit, Retrieve, Reuse, is a not for profit, intergovernmental organisation, governed by the statutes⁶² of member states and organisations. ISSN IC manages the identification and the description of serial publications and ongoing resources, print and online, in any subject.

⁵⁸ <https://github.com/ror-community/ror-records?tab=readme-ov-file#ror-records>

⁵⁹ <https://github.com/ror-community/ror-developer-docs/wiki/Developer-guidelines>

⁶⁰ https://portal.issn.org/services#list_submission

⁶¹ <https://www.issn.org/>

⁶² <https://www.issn.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/09/Statuts-du-Centre-avec-pdg1.pdf>

Criteria	IDSR Score	Discussion
IDS information security compatibility*	Medium	Has no certification yet but has been audited for ISO27001 and on path to achieve it.
Existing expertise and alignment	Low	The service lacks a public API, it has an ontology and managed ontologies of the data held within it. It uses MARC21 for book metadata held within the system. It doesn't offer a SPARQL method of querying data which seems to be preferred for the IDS Vocabulary Provider.
Infrastructure	Low	VM based deployment with Docker applications. Has no public API, no DDoS mitigations but does have firewalls in place. A partial audit trail is maintained. No SLA is provided.
Global presence	Medium-high	Aims to be a global service, though it is quite new (launched September 2023), so still scaling up and finding users. Data processing happens in France.
Data management	Medium	~4Gb data is managed. Username/password is used for authentication. A partial audit trail is maintained. Has no public API, so no self-descriptive endpoints and does not handle PII.
Software development & sustainability	Medium	Unsure if there are any policies around software quality. 4 FTEs out of 13 work in the technical division, supported by 3 additional contractors.
Standards	High	Has taken an active part in defining the ISSN standard ISO3297. Uses MARC21 (ISO2709) formatted records within the system.

*This section only assessed and scored for IDS-compatible information security and does not reflect any other information security the organisation may have.

App Store Providers and IDS Clearing House

Whilst OpenAIRE's EOSC Marketplace was initially considered for the App Store Provider role, and OpenAIRE's EOSC and OA Switchboard for an IDS Clearing House role, these were subsequently excluded after discussions with the organisations about these services and the IDS roles. 67 Bricks has therefore been unable to identify any services that might be suitable to fulfil either of these roles with the publishing and scholarly industry.

Organisations identified but not included in the analysis

CHORUS was identified as a potential Metadata Broker, however, they were unavailable for an interview or assessment within the period of research so we have been unable to include them at this stage.

IDS Readiness Score summary matrix

Services are listed below by role, then by highest IDS Readiness (IDSR) Score:

IDS role	Service/ Organisation	IDS Readiness Score*	IDS infosec compatibility**	IDS experience & alignment	Infras	Global presence and ops	Data management	Software dev & sustainability	Standards
Identity Provider	EZproxy/OCLC	Medium	Medium-high	Medium-low	High	High	Medium	Medium-high	Medium
	Identity and Access/LibLynx	Medium-low	Low	Medium-low	High	High	Medium	Medium	Medium
	TheIPRegistry.org/P SI	Low	Low	Low	Medium-low	Medium-high	Medium-high	Medium-low	Low
Metadata Broker	IA Scholar/Internet Archive	Medium	Medium	Medium-low	High	Medium-high	High	High	High
	Metadata Plus/Crossref	Medium	Medium-high	Medium-low	Medium-high	High	Medium	Medium-high	Medium
	Registry of OpenAIRE Graph/OpenAIRE	Medium	Low	Medium	High	High	Medium-high	Medium	High
	DataCite Commons/DataCite	Medium	Low	Medium-low	Medium-high	High	High	Medium-high	Medium
	Thoth	Medium	Low	Medium-low	High	High	Medium-high	Medium	Medium
	OA Switchboard	Medium-low	Low	Low	Medium-high	High	Medium	High	Medium
	OAeBU Workflows/COKI	Medium-low	Low	Low	Medium	Medium-high	Medium	Medium	High
	DOAB/OAPEN	Medium-low	Low	Medium-low	Medium-low	High	Medium-low	Medium	Medium
Vocabulary Provider	ROR	Medium-low	Low	Low	Medium-high	High	Medium-high	High	Medium
	Submit, Retrieve, Reuse/ISSN	Medium-low	Medium	Low	Low	Medium-high	Medium	Medium	High

*IDS Readiness Score is calculated as a weighted average of each of the seven sections. Weighting can be found in the 'IDS Readiness Scoring criteria' section in the Methodology.

** This section only assessed and scored for IDS-compatible information security and does not reflect any other information security the organisation may have.

Summary analysis

The specification for all five of the IDS services is highly specific, relying on particular message shapes which are unique to itself, and as such, unless an organisation has gone out of their way to implement an IDS service, they would not have created it. All organisations included in this work have developed their service specifically to deliver a specific service or function for their community, and unsurprisingly, not as a specific role within an IDS. This means that all services analysed have scored low on alignment to IDS and all organisations would need to undertake fairly significant development to create a service that is aligned with the IDS RAM.

Lots of organisations were identified as having good alignment with the Metadata Broker role, as highlighted in the Summary Matrix. This is unsurprising as many of the services within the industry have been developed to index content and associated metadata specifically to enable the dissemination, discoverability, and access to Open Access books. Out of the eight analysed, the Internet Archive Scholar was the most closely aligned.

Vocabulary Providers have scored somewhat lower than Metadata Brokers and Identity providers. This may be due to how the Vocabulary Provider in an IDS isn't responsible for defining vocabularies, rather, its function is to host the vocabularies for participants to query. Persistent Identifiers (PID) authorities, such as ROR and ISSN IC, that were selected to be interviewed for the role were primarily selected because they would be responsible for defining and providing the vocabularies. It may be a choice by a data provider (or the IDS operator) to use a PID in the dataset, but the PID authority is not required to be included in the IDS in any way. As such, there was a mismatch which contributed to the lower scores.

67 Bricks were unable to identify any services that might be able to fulfil the role of the Clearing House. This is perhaps because tracking and settlement isn't something typically done as a single service, but rather aspects of the role are integrated throughout the publishing workflow and across different platforms. For example, platform providers may use ecommerce solutions such as FoxyCart or Stripe to handle transactions, but these services lack large parts of the clearing house role. Specifically, they do not operate through an IDS connector and work for a single specific platform, not an entire ecosystem. We also did not identify any services in the industry that aligned with the App Store Providers role - this is likely because this is not a service or function typically needed within the industry. OpenAIRE looked initially promising for this role because they index software for searching in Explore, but they do not host and make this software available via containers as the IDS would expect for the App Store Provider.

No organisation interviewed was less than 2 years old. Meaning they would all meet one of the SCOSS criteria⁶³ for age and are considered stable.

High levels of information security is typically lacking amongst organisations specialising in open data. Whilst all organisations interviewed had security systems in place, very few have strived to implement a formal certification such as ISO27001, likely because it is such a large endeavour to achieve. These groups of open data organisations may actively avoid having PII within their data sets to avoid issues relating to GDPR, and some just don't need to consider the issue since the very nature of the data is about published content, meaning much of the data is already publicly available. However as the IDS operational certification is based heavily on the IS27001 certification and therefore has extremely high infosec criteria, this is a large gap for organisations to close and is a major gap found across the industry that would need addressing.

Education is required, during the interviews, it became readily apparent that most organisations had no or very limited knowledge of data spaces. They had even less

⁶³ <https://scoss.org/need-funding-for-open-infra/>

knowledge of any specific implementations such as IDS. This is not surprising as the IDS is a relatively new concept and has largely been developing within other industries (e.g. manufacturing, supply chains, energy etc).

Limitations of the research

There are natural limitations to the research method used, as some organisations have a multitude of products where parts of several (when considered together) may have better alignment with a single IDS role than just a single product. Some of the core services are easier to build out than others, the Metadata Broker has high alignment with many services (e.g. every search aggregator/depository could be considered to have high alignment as the core mechanism of providing a means of searching over a distributed body of work is their core purpose), but the App Store Provider has incredibly limited alignment to existing services. This should not be interpreted that there is no organisation within the scholarly communications industry that could not fulfil this role, rather that it is simply a different role to what is already needed in the landscape.

ANALYST OPINION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Deployment of an IDS for Open Access book usage and wider possible use cases such as closed books or journals usage data would be best served by having a single, well administered IDS over numerous ones to support multiple scholarly outputs. There is a non-trivial cost in setting up the core services of an IDS, so preference would lean towards few organisations operating many services. This can evolve, but simplicity, repeatability and accountability suggests fewer core organisations being included. This would also infer that there should be a single Metadata Broker for all content and data sets over multiple separate brokers, although a single IDS can contain multiple Metadata Brokers that may support diversity of scholarly outputs.

Data spaces offer an interesting solution for other problems faced within scholarly communications outside of OA book usage data. The issue of content distribution has been a regular issue faced by 67 bricks when developing content delivery platforms. There could be tremendous value in having a data space focused on sharing content between indexes and depositories, meaning a platform only has to integrate with one, clearly defined platform to disseminate this data.

When selecting organisations that could form part of an IDS, future preference should be given to organisations who have already achieved or are on the path of achieving ISO27001, SOC2 or FedRAMP certifications. This is because these are costly to achieve and a similar standard is required for IDS operational certification.

67 Bricks recommends that OAeBUDT works with a scholarly communications industry technology partner in selecting an appropriate implementation partner, providing insight, guidance and project management where OAeBUDT may be resource limited and value a deep technical understanding of the industry and software and processes used within it.

There are multiple paths forward that could be considered to deliver an MVP IDS:

1. Use a Data Space as a Service (DSaaS), like Sovity, a specialist in dataspace, to do all the work in setting up the IDS and operating it for the Trust.
2. Build and deploy a dataspace within scholarly communication using partners from both IDS and scholarly communication to jointly build a dataspace.
3. Build a simpler proof of concept just within scholarly communication using pre-existing open source dataspace components to see if it can be done without involving IDS specialists.
4. Organise an open innovation competition to source solutions for building an MVP IDS. Invite startups, tech companies, and innovators from around the world to submit proposals and prototypes, with the most promising submissions receiving funding, support, and mentorship to further develop and implement their IDS solutions.

OAeBUDT should choose a partner or series of partners who have knowledge of both IDS architectures and the domain of scholarly communications (such as 67 Bricks) to support in the IDS model development and technical roadmapping, and in the designing, building and operating of the OAEbUDT-IDS. IDS is still evolving and IDSA still hasn't published standards covering the entire solution. The Data Space Protocol⁶⁴ is also still being developed. As such, not even IDSA approved solution implementation partners could be considered a 9 in terms of technical readiness of an IDS. Although many implementation partners have had experience developing other types of data spaces and been involved in the evolution and design of IDS, an industry partner would complement any IDS-technical partner in closing any gaps in knowledge and help to work with the organisations and work towards the right solutions.

It is clear, as the champions for an IDS, there is a need for OAEbUDT to educate and inspire organisations within scholarly communications to understand and see the value in an OAEbUDT-IDS. Industry outreach events and workshops would give more context for the value proposition, and help to round out industry stakeholders' understanding of the benefits of an OAEbUDT-IDS.

⁶⁴ <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/v/dataspace-protocol/overview/readme>

APPENDIX - QUESTIONNAIRE TEMPLATE

67 Bricks Interview structure for OA Books Usage Data Trust: [organisation name]

Part 1: Introductions and background

- Introductions (67 Bricks staff members and interviewee)
- Background to OAeBUDT and the project:
 - OAeBUDT recently received a grant to focus on the development of “governance building blocks” for the OAeBUDT in line with the Design Principles for International Data Spaces (IDS) and specifications for data space certification.
 - We (67 Bricks) are aiming to understand which organisations may be able to perform one (or more) of the five core IDS core services in an MVP data space for OA book usage data, and how much additional development would be needed for them to achieve certification.
 - The five services we are looking at are Metadata Broker, Clearing House, Vocabulary Provider, Identity Provider, and App Store Provider.
 - **[Service] has been identified as potentially filling the role of [core IDS intermediary].**
- Discussion of the organisation and identified service
- Publication of a final report:
 - The full responses to this questionnaire will not be made public, but the information collected from it will be summarised at a very high level in a report for the OAeBUDT, which will be published.
 - All organisations will be given the opportunity to see the report before it is published.
- Any questions before we begin with the structured questionnaire?

Part 2: Questionnaire

General organisation questions

GO1. What is the country of incorporation for your organisation? [NTA-001]

GO2. Is your organisation primarily staffed by volunteers or employed staff? [NTA-005]

GO3. Is your organisation [NTA-006]:

- a. Less than 1 year old?
- b. 1 year or older, but less than 2 years old?
- c. 2 years or older, but less than 10 years old?
- d. 10 years or older?

GO4. How many staff work within your organisation? (approx. full time equivalents) [NTA-005]

GO5. How many staff work within the technical division of your organisation? (approx. full time equivalents) [NTA-005]

GO6. Has your organisation taken part in defining any standards? (yes/no/unsure)

GO7. Have you ever built a service or a proof of concept for taking part in any data space (e.g. International Data Spaces)? (yes/no/unsure)

GO8. Have you achieved any level of certification from IDS? If so, which level? (yes + certification/no/unsure)

GO9. Has the organisation ever cooperated with another on developing a service? If so, which services? (yes + service/no/unsure)

GO10. Does your organisation have a quality assurance strategy? If so, can we have a copy? If not, can you describe the processes, tools and approaches used to ensure the quality of systems developed within the organisation? (yes + copy or description/no/unsure)

Organisation level information security questions

OS1. Have you achieved any third party certifications around information security and best practices such as ISO27001, Cyber Essentials (Plus), SOC2 or others? (yes + certification name/no/unsure)

OS2. Have you had any known security incidents in the past 5 years?

General service questions

This section of the interview should be repeated for each service identified within the organisation we want to consider for this work.

S1. What is the name of the service?

S2. Which countries does this service serve? [NTA-002]

S3. Which country does data processes occur in? [NTA-003]

S4. What types/schemas of data does the service manage? [NTA-004]

S5. How large are the datasets managed by the service (GBs of disk space)? [NTA-004]

S6. What is the main technology stack used?

S7. How is the service deployed? Is it on-prem or cloud based (if cloud, which ones?)

S8. Does it make use of Docker or containerisation? [OS01] (yes/no/unsure)

S9. Do you have a defined SLA for the service, if so what is it? (yes + metrics/no/unsure)

S10. Have you ever failed to maintain the SLA within the past 3 years of operation? (yes/no/unsure)

S11. Does this system conform to any standards not defined within your organisation? If yes, which ones? (yes + standards/no/unsure)

S12. Does the service have an API that describes itself (e.g. OpenAPI/Swagger definition)? [INF01] (yes/no/unsure)

Service level information security questions

SS1. Does the service use certificates for authentication? [COM02] (yes/no/unsure)

SS2. Does the service log each access control decision? [AUD01] (yes/no/unsure)

SS3. Does the service allow human users to authenticate and make use of it? [CR1.1] (yes/no/unsure)

SS4. Does the service record auditable events, such as authentication, request errors, system errors, backup and restore events, config updates and audit log events? [CR2.8] (yes/no/unsure)

SS5. Does the service have a mechanism to defend against DDoS attacks? [CR7.1] (yes/no/unsure)

SS6. How is the network secured that the service operates within (e.g. Firewalls, intrusion detection system etc.) [A.13.1]?

SS7. Does your system require you to respect rules around data protection or personally identifiable information? [A.18.1] (yes/no/unsure)

IDS service-specific questions

Subsections should only be asked for IDS core components identified that the service being questioned about could meet.

Metadata Broker Service

MB1. Does the service index book metadata? (yes/no/unsure)

MB2. If so, does it use any defined schemas and what are they? (yes + schemas/no/unsure)

MB3. Does the service provide linking to other services you or other organisations run? (yes/no/unsure)

MB4. Does the service have an API or UI that is accessible to users? If so, what technologies does it use? (yes + technologies/no/unsure)

Clearing House

CH1. Does your service store audit data? (yes/no/unsure)

CH2. How do you ensure integrity of that audit data?

CH3. Does the service have an API or UI that is accessible to users? If so, what technologies does it use? (yes + technologies/no/unsure)

CH4. Does this service handle financial transactions? Does this service track and ensure these transactions are settled between parties?

App Store Provider

1. Do you provide software for downstream users to install and run themselves? (yes/no/unsure)

2. How do you host this software and make it available for consumption?

Vocabulary Provider

1. Does the service handle structured book metadata formats? If so, which ones? (yes + formats/no/unsure)

2. Is the service responsible for managing ontologies? If so, which ones? (yes + ontologies/no/unsure)

3. Does the service have an API or UI that is accessible to users? If so, what technologies does it use? (yes + technologies/no/unsure)

4. Is your ontology expressed using RDF? (yes/no/unsure)

5. Can it be queried using SPARQL? (yes/no/unsure)

Identity Provider

1. Does the service provide authentication services to third-parties? If so, through which mechanism(s) is this achieved? (yes + mechanism/no/unsure)

2. Does the service issue and manage X.509 certificates? (yes/no/unsure)